

FDO Bulletin 2021-1 May 2021

FDO Forum

The FDO Forum is an initiative that brings together experts who see the concept of FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) as a major contribution to master the challenges posed by the digital transformation in society, economy and science. The Forum seeks to advance the concept in all respects up to detailed technical specifications of its components and the required infrastructure services. It will therefore closely collaborate with initiatives such as RDA, CODATA, WDS, DONA, IDF and GO FAIR.

In October 2019, the RDA GEDE initiative invited 28 data experts from different countries to a workshop in Paris to synchronise on the concept of FDO. The meeting ended with agreement on the huge potential of FDO to structure the future space of digital entities in a sustainable way, on the FDO Framework allowing different implementations of the FDO concept and on a process. Due to the engagement of some key persons in urgent initiatives (COVID-related) the uptake was delayed by roughly one year. In late 2020, a group of experts committed to the concept of FDO were invited to start the FDO Forum with the intention to foster all aspects related with FDOs based on the FDO Framework as agreed in the Paris workshop. ([Information about the Paris meeting and the FDOF](#))

Intensive discussions at regular meetings led to building the Steering Committee (SC), discussing proposals and accepting the first six Working Groups, and agreeing on a roadmap where a first well-prepared FDO conference will take place in September/October 2022. This conference can be seen as a milestone which will be prepared by a variety of workshops and working meetings. During the phase of RDA GEDE discussions, a large international group of experts interested in the concept of Digital Objects and then FAIR Digital Objects was formed. Together with newly registered experts we call this group the “FDO community”. Currently, the SC is discussing a communication and engagement strategy to achieve transparency with the goal to improve our interaction with the FDO community and the interested public. The FDO Forum is still in a start-up phase.

Although there will be a need for a proper governance structure, the FDO Forum decided to postpone these discussions to the first international FDO conference in 2022 to allow for flexibility as the work progresses. We will therefore adhere to the simple governance structure until there will be a decision. The FDO Forum will base its activities on the personal engagement of its members, i.e., it will not compete for project funds. Funding should come from “in kind” and contributions of its members. This will limit the Forum’s capacity to deploy activities.

FDO Documents

The following key documents have been endorsed and are on the FDO Forum’s website (<https://fairdo.org>):

- The **Scoping Document** describes the scope of the activities of the FDO Forum and its current temporary organisational form. (<http://bit.ly/FDO-Documents>)
- The **Landscape Document** is a snapshot of the current groups active in the FDO Forum and their foci. (<http://bit.ly/FDO-Documents>)
- The **FDO Framework** has been taken over from the Paris workshop discussions and are seen as the baseline for the future specification work. (<http://bit.ly/FDO-Documents>)
- The **Base FDO Definition** document presents a basal definition of what an FDO is. (<http://bit.ly/FDO-Documents>)

In addition, the following documents are in preparation:

- A **Communication Strategy** to describe how the FDO Forum will disseminate its results and engage all stakeholders interested in FDOs.

- A first **Gap Analysis** presents a snapshot describing what still needs to be done to come to a fully functional FDO based infrastructure and will enable defining roadmaps.

Community Engagement

The main vehicle of work in the FDO Forum are the working groups. Members of the WGs are expected to be actively contributing to the discussions and work which requires substantial efforts. WGs are built on the basis of a request which needs to indicate a contribution to goals of the FDO Forum. The Steering Committee will decide about such requests. Each WG work is led by co-chairs who take responsibility to achieve progress together with the members who will be invited according to the WG's policy and requirements which will be made public via the website. The WGs are expected to make progress along the topics being identified and therefore will be limited in size.

Of course, many of the experts interested in the work of the FDO Forum will prefer to not take an active role in a WG. Nevertheless, there is a growing wish to not only get information about the progress at regular moments but to be involved in specific aspects of the FDO work. To address these wishes the FDO Forum will

- produce and disseminate quarterly **FDO bulletins**
- organise **Synchronisation Meetings** two times per year to which the FDO community will be invited
- evaluate **further possibilities** dependent on its capacity development.

The **first synchronisation meeting will be organised in September/October 2021**. Each WG will have the chance to present and discuss achievements and plans to offer ways for experts to give comments and to start an interaction. Documents endorsed by the FDO Forum will also be presented for open discussion. Depending on the progress, other forms such as hackathons or “plug-in” meetings will be organised.

In addition, all WGs may organise **open workshops** depending on their workplans.

Working Groups

Working Groups (WG) are the vehicles in the FDO Forum to achieve progress. Overlap between the WGs is anticipated in so far as certain topics will be addressed in different WGs from different perspectives. As overlap occurs, the WGs will define a method interaction, e.g. joint meetings, building task forces, etc. A basic principle is that WGs are responsible for their way of working as long as they set clear milestones, maintain a workshop plan to involve others in discussing their achievements, and contribute to the required convergence. For the overall goals of the WGs we refer to the website. Recent updates and results achieved include:

1. Technical Specification & Implementation Group (TSIG)

TSIG has met a few times. Currently, the following topics are being addressed and intensively discussed:

- **Base Definition** of FDO has been finished.
- **Gap Analysis** (first version being synchronised with all WGs is almost ready)
- Deep **Technical Specification** of an FDO including understanding issues such as scope, forms of FDOs, profiles, machine actionability, necessary validation procedures, etc.
- **Type System** as required for FDOs (collaborating with SEM and BIG)
- Implications of “**plugging-in**” a new set of metadata/data objects

2. Basic Infrastructure Group (BIG)

BIG just had its first meeting in May and will define its work plan with the goal to identify, specify and build the necessary infrastructure for FDOs such as a PID landscape ready to be used by every researcher.

3. Semantic Group (SEM)

This group will have its kick-off meeting in May and deal with the three major aspects: (1) Develop a Semantic Model of FDOs, (2) Specification of the requirements for an LD implementation of FDOs, and (3) Specifying semantic mapping relevant for FDOs.

4. Canonical Workflow Framework for Research (CWFR)

This group was started in the realm of the RDA GEDE collaboration to address urgent changes in the data practices in the many data labs. The two main pillars are to foster the transition towards libraries of

reusable workflow components and using the FDOs as glue and the basis to create FAIRness. CWFR will mainly organise working meetings addressing these two topics and thus contribute to the definition of FDOs.

5. FAIR Implementation Profiles & Practices (FIPP)

This group will extend its activities within the GOFAIR FIP initiative by taking up data practices in a broader sense and contribute the knowledge extracted from assessing data practices to help advance the FDO specification and implementation work.

6. eInfrastructure Group (eING)

This group has been established to work out a demonstrator that allows different types of repositories as maintained in eInfrastructure centres to be linked with the help of DO Interface Protocol supporting the FDO concept. The first version of a demonstrator will be made available before summer break 2021. Then the group will assess its further plans.

In addition, a group has been established to prepare the **1st International FDO Conference to be held in September/October 2022.**

Responsible for this FDO Bulletin are the FDO-SC Co-Chairs:
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